

How to Acknowledge Use of ARDC Services and Co-Investment Project Outputs and Services

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Related Documents	ARDC Acknowledgment Guidelines Persistent Identifiers for ARDC Investments How to Acknowledge the ARDC in a Co-Investment Partnership Project
Purpose	<p>This guideline is for users of ARDC services and ARDC partners.</p> <p>It outlines how users of ARDC services can acknowledge the use of ARDC services and ARDC co-investment project outputs.</p>

For users of ARDC Services: How to acknowledge use of ARDC services and co-investment project outputs and services

In line with the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) acknowledgement guidelines, users of services supported through ARDC are required to acknowledge the use of those services in publications using the standard text below:

For users of ARDC co-investment project outputs, such as platforms and national data assets:

- *This research used [insert name of platform/data asset and link to the platform/asset], a partnership between [insert names of lead partner or partners] and the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC). ARDC is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).*

For users of ARDC Services

For users of ARDC Nectar Research Cloud and supported services

- **ARDC Nectar Research Cloud:**

This research used the [Australian Research Data Commons \(ARDC\) Nectar Research Cloud](#). ARDC is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).

- **Services supported by the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud - including the ARDC Virtual Desktop Service, BinderHub Service, Jupyter Notebook Service:**

This research used the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) [Name of ARDC Service, e.g. Virtual Desktop Service, and link to the service]. The ARDC is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).

- **ARDC Nectar Research Cloud users with arrangements or support from specific cloud Nodes:**

This research used the [Australian Research Data Commons \(ARDC\) Nectar Research Cloud](#) supported by [Nectar Node Operator name here]. The ARDC is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).

- **For websites, platforms, services, databases that use the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud as infrastructure**

If you use the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud to support an ongoing website, service, portal, database etc, please use the following acknowledgements on your website and publications.

The [platform/website/service] is hosted by the [Australian Research Data Commons \(ARDC\) Nectar Research Cloud](#). The ARDC is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).

For users of other ARDC services

Other ARDC services include:

- [ARDC Research Data Australia](#)
- [ARDC Vocabularies Australia](#)
- [ARDC Research Link Australia](#)
- [ARDC Health Data Australia](#)
- [ARDC Community Data Lab](#)
- [Identifier Services](#).

Australian Research Data Commons

This research used the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) [name of ARDC service, and link to the service]. The ARDC is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).

Acknowledging the ARDC in a co-investment partnership project

For guidelines on how to acknowledge the ARDC in a co-investment partnership project, visit <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551786>.